

Hyperoperation Depth (Hyperdepth): Measuring How Hard a Number Is to Reach

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Abstract

Given the seed set $\{0, 1\}$ and the five hyperoperations – addition, multiplication, exponentiation, tetration, and pentation – how many steps does it take to reach an arbitrary non-negative integer n ? We define this count as the *hyperoperation depth* $\delta(n)$ and compute $\forall n \leq 100,000$, and look at what the results tell us. The depth values follow a skewed distribution with its tail pointing to the left. Numbers like 256 or 729 that sit neatly on power towers are cheap to reach while numbers whose shortest path requires many intermediate steps through addition, multiplication, and exponentiation take much longer.

1. Introduction

Hyperoperations are a family of binary operations where each one is just repeated application of the one before it, allowing them to grow fast. Addition is linear, multiplication is polynomial operation, and the output to exponentiation is much larger. While tetration and pentation are not used in day-to-day math, they grow even more quickly that even small inputs push past any practical bound almost immediately.

2. Why I Created This

Large numbers get out of hand fast. Once you go past a certain point, raw magnitude stops meaning anything useful, you can't intuitively compare 10^{100} and $10^{100} + 7$ in any meaningful way just by looking at them. I wanted a way to measure the structural complexity of a number rather than just referring to its size.

The idea is to treat 0 and 1 as atomic numbers, where they represent the smallest irreducible building blocks and ask how many hyperoperation steps it takes to construct any given number from them. The result is a single value, $\delta(n)$, that tells you how "far" a number is from those atoms in terms of structural complexity by operations. A number like 256 for example is structurally simple because it sits cleanly on a power tower built from 2s. A number like 710 requires a longer chain of steps through the lower operations before it can be reached, so its depth is much higher. You can kind of tell that this system of assessing numbers was inspired by the Kolmogorov Complexity, which determines the minimum amount of simple instructions to generate a piece of data. If a number was given and it does not 'look' like it follows any simple steps, then either refer to the number as the number itself or spend time mapping out the minimum amount of operational steps required to find the depth of it.

The seed set is not strictly fixed at $\{0, 1\}$. You can think of it as base b , where base b uses $\{0, 1, \dots, b-1\}$ as the atomic numbers. Base 2 is the default ($\{0, 1\}$), base 3 adds 2 to the seed, base 4 adds 0, 1, 2, 3, and so on. A larger seed base gives you more atoms to start from, which lowers the depth of most numbers and changes the distribution.

3. Definitions

Definition 1 (Hyperoperation depth). $\delta(n)$ is the minimum number of operational steps needed to produce exactly n , starting from the atomic numbers $\{0, 1\}$ and applying hyperoperations from the highest available down to addition at each step. Note that adding parentheses do not count as operations, for instance $256 \rightarrow (2 \uparrow\uparrow 2) \uparrow\uparrow 2$, $\delta(256) = 5$. The hyperoperation index theoretically extends to $k \rightarrow \infty$, though the computation here is bounded at $k = 5$. The operations used are:

$$H_1(a, b) = a + b \tag{1}$$

$$H_2(a, b) = a \cdot b \tag{2}$$

$$H_3(a, b) = a \uparrow b \tag{3}$$

$$H_4(a, b) = a \uparrow^2 b \tag{4}$$

$$H_5(a, b) = a \uparrow^3 b \tag{5}$$

Proposition 1. $\delta(n)$ is finite for every non-negative integer n .

Proof. Since 1 is in the seed set and $H_1(a, 1) = a + 1$, every integer k is reachable by k additions, so $\delta(k) \leq k$. □

Remark 1. $\delta(n)$ is not monotone, meaning the function's output does not follow a strict relationship with n . For 256 as seen above, has $\delta(256) = 5$ because it sits directly on a power tower. $\delta(257) = 6$ and $\delta(255) = 12$ because neither can be reached directly by a high hyperoperation from the seed set as both require longer chains through lower operations. Being one away from a power-tower number can cost seven extra steps.

4. Results

Depth was computed for all $n \in [0, 100,000]$ using a breadth-first search, and programmed using the fastest programming language I was familiar with, that being C, with overflow checks to keep arithmetic bounded. Results for $[0, 1,000]$ are shown in Table 1, and the full $[0, 100,000]$ distribution in Table 2.

The distribution is right-skewed in both cases, with a long sparse tail at high depths. The peak sits around depth 13 for $[0, 1,000]$ and depth 20 for $[0, 100,000]$. The maximum depth grows as the range expands: 17 at 10^3 , 25 at 10^5 .

The 7 hardest-to-reach numbers in $[0, 1,000]$, all at depth 17, are:

$$\{710, 862, 863, 939, 940, 943, 995\}$$

At the $[0, 100,000]$ scale, 31 numbers sit at the maximum depth of 25, all concentrated above 89,000 (see below).

Table 1: Depth distribution over $[0, 1,000]$.

Depth	Count	Depth	Count
0	2	9	57
1	1	10	91
2	1	11	111
3	1	12	156
4	6	13	189
5	5	14	161
6	13	15	105
7	27	16	35
8	33	17	7

Table 2: Depth distribution over $[0, 100,000]$.

Depth	Count	Depth	Count
0	2	13	1,081
1	1	14	1,852
2	1	15	3,124
3	1	16	5,030
4	7	17	7,927
5	6	18	11,670
6	16	19	15,638
7	34	20	18,314
8	51	21	17,153
9	110	22	11,470
10	199	23	4,541
11	339	24	771
12	632	25	31

We can see that the numbers that are easy to reach tend to sit directly on power towers or are products of small reachable numbers and the numbers at greater depths require longer chains of steps, often passing through addition, multiplication, and exponentiation before arriving at the target. None of the higher operations produce them directly but can be used alongside other smaller-order hyperoperations to produce exact n .

5. The Issue

Being fully honest here, your only fate is to be creative with what I invented. After all, this was a hobby project to think of and get to working on so I haven't really thought of a good use at all and I'm leaving it up to you.

6. Open Questions

1. Can the inversion hardness of δ be formally proved, or reduced to a known hard problem?
2. What happens to the distribution for $n \leq 10^6$? Does the skew persist, and where

does the peak land?

3. How does δ change if the seed set is different, e.g. $\{0, 1, 2\}$?
4. How does restricting the allowed operations affect depth? Allowing only the lower operations means bigger jumps are no longer possible in a single step, which would push most numbers to greater depths.
5. Is there a closed-form bound for $\delta(n)$ for specific families of numbers: powers of 2, primes, factorials?

7. Integer Sequence

Table 3: $\delta(n)$ for $n \in [0, 100]$

n	+0	+1	+2	+3	+4	+5	+6	+7	+8	+9
0	0	0	1	2	3	4	4	5	4	4
10	5	6	6	7	7	7	4	5	6	7
20	7	8	8	9	7	6	7	4	5	6
30	7	8	6	7	7	8	6	7	8	9
40	9	10	10	9	10	9	10	11	7	7
50	8	8	9	10	6	7	7	8	8	9
60	9	10	10	10	6	7	8	9	9	10
70	10	11	8	9	9	9	10	11	10	11
80	9	6	7	8	8	9	10	9	10	11
90	10	11	12	11	12	12	9	10	9	10
100	7									

A barely logarithmic relationship can be seen, but the relationship between n and $\delta(n)$ is not 'strictly' logarithmic as that is incorrect if assumed so.

8. Conclusion

The hyperoperation depth assigns every non-negative integer a measure of how far it is from 0 and 1 under the hyperoperations. The distribution shows negative skew where numbers that can be recreated with mostly power-towers sit at very low depths, whereas a thin tail of structurally plain numbers are the hardest to reach. The function may have some cryptographic interest, where numbers can be encrypted into their depths, due to its non-linearity and the apparent hardness of inversion, but the key gap is a formal hardness proof, which remains open.